

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-116-IBN-5-5% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	117	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 116
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/15/2022 8:59:12 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 8:24:10 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.950	1409082	50.23	187433
2	6.305	1396173	49.77	174287

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-115-IBN-5-5% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	5	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 115
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/15/2022 9:10:21 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 8:24:27 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.962	160685	2.59	19988
2	6.305	6050328	97.41	778797